

Balanced-Detection Interferometric Cavity-Assisted Photothermal Spectroscopy via collimating Fiber-Array integration

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ABSTRACT

This work reports on the implementation of a fiber-array with attached microlenses in the Balanced-Detection Interferometric Cavity-Assisted Photothermal Spectroscopy (BICAPS) scheme, enabling a highly compact probe laser beam path. The sample probe and the reference beam were coupled into a 1-mm spaced Fabry-Pérot interferometer with a lateral beam separation of only 1.25 mm. A Quantum Cascade Laser was used to induce photo-thermal waves, which were detected via the probe laser beam. The reference probe beam was used to realize balanced detection, allowing for significant noise reduction. The sensor's metrological figures of merit were evaluated by detection of nitric oxide. For the targeted absorption band centered at 1900.08 cm^{-1} a 1σ minimum detection limit of 64 ppbv was achieved with a 1-second integration time. This performance corresponds to a normalized noise equivalent absorption of $5.7 \times 10^{-8} \text{ cm}^{-1} \text{ W Hz}^{-1/2}$.

1 INTRODUCTION

Optical sensors leverage the ability of light to investigate the properties of matter in all its phases, from solid and liquid to gas, offering insights into qualitative information such as the molecular structure and composition as well as quantitative information on selected target analytes present in the sample under investigation with short analysis times. Many aspects of life quality, such as air quality monitoring, food analysis, and health diagnosis, benefit from continued improvements in optical sensors. [1]–[3]. Fundamentally, spectroscopy utilizes the unique characteristic of molecules to absorb light at specific wavelengths, employing the distinctive absorption spectrum of each molecule as a fingerprint for its detection and identification [4].

Classical laser absorption spectroscopy (LAS) relies on the significant absorption of many gases in the mid-IR spectrum, but it faces limitations in miniaturization since the sensitivity diminishes with shorter interaction pathlengths, according to the Lambert-Beer law. In this context, Photo-Thermal Spectroscopy (PTS) stands out for its ability to detect gases in very small sensing volumes [5]–[8]. When modulated light is absorbed by a sample, it induces a periodic heating cycle of the sample, which in turn generates thermal and pressure waves. PTS is based on the principle of detecting these thermal waves whereas Photo-Acoustic Spectroscopy (PAS) detects acoustic waves produced by the periodic expansions and contractions of the sample [9].

Indirect spectroscopy techniques, such as PTS and PAS, are baseline-free detection and show large dynamic range (of many orders of magnitude) which important practical advantages [10]. Baseline-free detection drastically simplifies signal processing and occurs because in the absence of targeted gas particles in the sensor, no signal is generated,

eliminating the challenges associated with reflection and scattering effects, that are typically dominant in LAS at low absorption levels. Additionally, unlike absorption spectroscopy, the analytical signal generated in this technique is directly proportional to the power of the excitation laser.

The core components of a PTS system include an excitation laser and a transducer [11]. The excitation laser heats the sample while the transducer converts the thermal effects induced by light absorption into a measurable signal. Among several types of transducers and detection techniques, such as piezoelectric transducers [12], cantilevers, and deflection or thermal lens techniques [13]–[15], an optical interferometer is an ideal element for highly sensitive PTS gas detection. It serves to detect the change of refractive index induced by the temperature change. The light that propagates inside the interferometer experiences a phase shift that is directly proportional to the refractive index. Different types of interferometers have been used such as the Mach Zehnder interferometer (MZI), which finds extensive application in both free-space and in all-fiber setups [16], as well as multi-pass cells or micro- and nano-engineered optical fibers, as hollow core fibers (HCF) [6], [17]–[19] and the recently reported antiresonant HCF (ARHCF) [20], [21]. Those all-fibers setups overcome several drawbacks such as a lack of compactness, but still suffer from slow response times and limited spectral region, given by the intrinsic fiber attenuation [6].

Fabry-Pérot (FP) cavities are widely used in spectroscopy [22] and photothermal spectroscopy employing an FP cavity as a transducer for the detection of photo-induced changes is a very powerful gas-sensing approach and is known as the *Interferometric Cavity-Assisted Photothermal Spectroscopy* (ICAPS) technique [7], [23], [24]. ICAPS has proven highly suitable for sensitive and compact gas detection by application of an air-spaced FP cavity with a small mirror spacing and a moderate cavity finesse. Refined architectures of the basic ICAPS method have achieved sensitivities down to the single-digit parts-per-billion by volume (ppbv) range [23], [24]. The FP cavity type exhibits favorable characteristics such as simplicity and the potential for sensor miniaturization [25].

Recently, balanced-detection ICAPS (BICAPS) has emerged as an important strategy to mitigate noise and enhance signal-to-noise ratio (SNR), thus providing a lower detection limit. The balanced-detection methodology, which combines information from the sample and reference signals from two detectors, effectively suppresses common-mode noise, offering a pathway to more reliable and precise gas sensing techniques [23], [24]. The improved sensitivity of BICAPS and robustness against noise comes at the cost of an increased system complexity, i.e., the use of two identical FPIs within the same gas cell, one serving as probe and the other as a reference path.

This work presents the integration of a fiber-coupled microlens array into a balanced-detection ICAPS measurement, improving the compactness of the fiber-coupled probe laser path. The small dimension of the array allows coupling the sample probe and reference beam, with a lateral spacing of a few hundreds of micrometers (μm), into the FPI mirrors. With its capability to process optical signals in parallel, the fiber array represents an important step towards simplifying and compacting the architecture of the system.

Fiber arrays are ubiquitous in the field of photonic integrated circuit (PIC) based optical communications [26]. Advances in PIC manufacturing and the utilization of a variety of platforms (e.g., SiN) allow photonic applications to extend into biomedical and sensing space [27], allowing for very compact and cost-effective solutions. To the best of our knowledge this publication marks the first demonstration of a gas sensor based on photothermal interferometry using a microlensed-fiber array. Through this approach, the presented work advances fiber-array-based gas sensing technologies, maintaining high sensitivity and robustness to noise while adding operational simplicity and compactness to the system's architecture and processing.

The sensor's figures of merit were established by measuring nitric oxide (NO) at wavenumbers around 1900 cm^{-1} . Detecting NO is important due to its significant role in environmental and biological processes. Environmentally, NO contributes to air pollution, smog, and acid rain, making it crucial to monitor for air quality control. In healthcare, NO is essential for understanding and managing heart and lung diseases, as it regulates blood pressure and contributes to the body's immune response [28]–[30].

2 METHODS

2.1 $2f$ -WM Basic ICAPS Principle and Balanced Detection

The first reported ICAPS experiment demonstrated the benefits of employing a FPI as a transducer for photothermal spectroscopy, in combination with wavelength modulation (WM) and second harmonic ($2f$) detection, to enhance both SNR and the technique's selectivity [7], [23], [24], [31]. The $2f$ -WM technique involves modulating the excitation laser's wavelength at a frequency f and detecting a signal at the second harmonic ($2f$). $2f$ -WM detection presents multiple advantages [32]. Firstly, it shifts the signal at higher frequencies, eliminating the DC component and reducing

the $1/f$ noise (or flicker noise). Secondly, the $2f$ -signal, being dependent on the curvature of the absorption line rather than to the absolute peak level, increases at lower pressures, where the linewidth narrows, thereby reducing the impact of broader background absorptions on the measurements.

The FPI working principle is very well described in the literature [33]. The FPI is an optical cavity consisting of two parallel mirrors spaced by a distance d , which partially reflect the light. The space between the mirrors may be filled with matter, such as air or other gases, having the refractive index n . Only a discrete number of equally spaced frequencies λ_{res} can resonate within the FP cavity – specifically those whose round-trip phase-shift ($\Delta\varphi$) is an integer multiple of 2π :

$$\Delta\varphi = \frac{2\pi}{\lambda_{res}} 2nd\cos(\theta) = 2m\pi. \quad (1)$$

The resonance frequencies depend on d and on the refractive index n of the material in between the mirrors, with θ the angle of incidence. By engineering d and choosing n , one can select the frequencies of the standing waves within the cavity. The reflected and transmitted intensities, as function of $\Delta\varphi$ and the cavity finesse, are described by the Airy function [33]. The finesse (F) quantifies the sharpness of the resonance peaks and is a measure of the cavity's ability to resolve spectral lines. The finesse is defined as the ratio of the free spectral range (FSR) to the full width at half maximum ($FWHM$) of the resonance peaks.

Fig. 2 FPI reflection spectrum at an initial refractive index n_1 and after photo-induced temperature change and therefore refractive index change n_2 . Higher temperature induces a decrease in the refractive index ($n_2 < n_1$)

The basic ICAPS principle detecting the FPI's reflectance is schematically shown in Figure 2. In the ICAPS scheme, the probe laser (green dashed line) is tuned near the inflection point at one side of the resonance (red curve). The inflection point is chosen as corresponds to the steepest part of the resonance curve and thus gives the maximum sensitivity. The steepness, or sensitivity of the FPI depends on the finesse, which, in turn, depends on the mirror's reflectivity, as well as on factors such as mirrors alignment, flatness, and surface quality.

The inflection point is located at approximately 25% of the top of the function. Near this specific position, and within a narrow range around it, the resonance curve also achieves its maximum linearity, also making the sensor highly linear in this region. The signal intensity recorded at the photodiode when the probe laser is locked near the inflection point and when the refractive index within the FP cavity is n_1 is defined in Figure 2 as I_{n1} . As the refractive index n_1 between the mirrors of the FPI changes to n_2 due to photo-induced temperature changes resulting from the absorption of excitation light and subsequent release of heat, the resonance position shifts (blue curve). Consequently, this shift leads to a change in the intensity detected by the photodiode, which is represented by I_{n2} in Figure 2.

When the excitation laser is modulated at a frequency f_{exc} , the sample within the FP cavity experiences a periodic density modulation, which in turn induces a periodic refractive index modulation, between indices n_1 and n_2 . Due to the oscillation of the refractive index, the resonance and the inflection point oscillate at the same frequency f_{exc} . Consequently, the signal recorded by the photodiode exhibits a component at f_{exc} (proportional to the intensity difference ΔI), but also at its harmonics, including $2f_{exc}$, $3f_{exc}$ and so forth. In all techniques which use $2f$ -WM principle, the detection of the $2f_{exc}$ component is achieved using a lock-in-amplifier (LIA).

Balanced-Detection ICAPS is a powerful method for noise reduction down up to the sensor's fundamental shot noise limit. Balanced detection cancels two of primary sources of noise: the probe laser's frequency and intensity fluctuations, as well as environmental disturbances caused e.g. by acoustic waves [23], [24]. The probe laser excess noise adds additional noise in the probe beam path, whereas environmental disturbances may induce unwanted changes in the refractive index inside the cavity, impacting the transmission function characteristics and therefore the resonance position. In BICAPS, the probe laser is split evenly by a beam splitter before coupled into two individual FP cavities. The system employs two identical optical paths, each subjected to the same probe laser and environmental noise. However, one pathway crosses the excitation beam and therefore is influenced by the photothermal effect, while the other is not, as it is spatially displaced. The beam that experiences the photothermal effect is referred to as the "sample probe beam", whereas the beam used as reference for noise detection is called the "reference probe beam". For balanced operation, the reflectance of each channel is detected by a separate photodiode. The signals of the two photodiodes are then subtracted by a differential amplifier, enabling cancellation of identical noise (common-mode noise) in both parts with high rejection ratio, improving the system's SNR.

2.2 Microlensed fiber-array

The fiber-array (FA) is widely used in optical telecommunication, fiber-optic sensors, spectroscopy, and packaging of photonics integrated circuits (PICs) [26], [34]–[36], where precise alignment and coupling of multiple optical fibers is necessary. In FAs, the individual fibers are assembled on substrates, typically constructed from silicon or silica, and aligned within designated v-grooves. These fibers are arranged in either an array or a 2D matrix. The spacing between the fibers generally follows PICs standards, with common pitch sizes of $127\ \mu\text{m}$ or $250\ \mu\text{m}$, although customization is possible based on specific application.

Fig. 3 Schematic of the fiber-array with collimating microlens array. Inset: Microscopic image of two microlenses.

In the context of our work, the FA comprises six fibers arranged linearly with a pitch of $250\ \mu\text{m}$, and incorporates a microlens array (MLA), as illustrated in Figure 3. The main body of the FA is made in Tempax and has geometrical dimensions of $2.5\ \text{mm} \times 10\ \text{mm} \times 1.5\ \text{mm}$, while the MLA has dimensions of $1.62\ \text{mm} \times 0.8\ \text{mm} \times 1\ \text{mm}$. MLA is manufactured by Axetris, while the FA is manufactured and assembled to the MLA by Meisu Optics. Light can be launched through six FC/APC connectors, each of which is connected to an individual output fiber. This FA configuration enables access to each fiber with a specific power, wavelength, polarization and so on. The optical fibers are polarization-maintaining and specifically engineered for operation at a wavelength of $1550\ \text{nm}$. The PM1550 fibers

exhibit a mode-field beam diameter of $10.5 \pm 0.5 \mu\text{m}$ at the operating wavelength. These fibers are characterized by numerical aperture $\text{NA} = 0.12$, and by a divergence angle of $\sim 50 \text{ mrad}$. Due to this significant divergence, the fibers are unsuitable for direct integration with a planar FPI: FPI requires beam collimation to maintain high finesse. Here, the collimation capability of the MLA becomes crucial, significantly impacting the system efficiency and accuracy. The MLA is aligned and assembled with the fiber-array with sub-micrometer precision. This precise alignment ensures that each fiber across the entire array produces a beam with almost identical waist size and divergence angle. The uniformity of the output beams also depends critically on the microlens array. It is crucial that each microlens is fabricated with precision to guarantee consistent optical performance across the array. In applications where precise beam collimation is essential, e.g., for pluggable PIC optical connections [34], [35] integrating a FA with an MLA is fundamental. In systems such as Fabry-Pérot cavities, where the beam must be collimated to achieve constructive interference with itself on each round trip, this integration is also very important. The MLA used in this work is designed to achieve a working distance of 30 mm and a $1/e^2$ beam diameter of $200 \mu\text{m}$. The natural divergence of the output collimated beam is calculated to be 4.93 mrad, while we measured a beam divergence of 7.1 mrad.

A pitch of $250 \mu\text{m}$ and a beam diameter of $200 \mu\text{m}$ will lead to crosstalk between adjacent channels. To minimize the risk of crosstalk for short distances, the mode field diameter (MDF) of the collimated beam should be less than 55% of the fiber pitch. However, with the increase in the number of reflections, beam divergence becomes a more prominent issue, requiring a greater separation between the channels. This subject will be discussed in more detail in Section 3.2. Incorporating a collimating fiber-array into BICAPS ensures beams with almost identical optical properties, and therefore practically equal noise characteristics. As the beams are closer when impacting the mirrors, the cavity's optical response to each beam is more similar, ensuring better accuracy and reliability in measurements. Moreover, the use of a fiber-array miniaturizes the BICAPS system, leading to a potential more portable setup. On the other hand, aligning the two beams within a single fiber-array is more complex. Unlike systems where beams can be aligned separately, any adjustment affects both paths, necessitating greater precision. Thus, while the collimating fiber-array in BICAPS offers a compact, unified, and simplified system with consistent noise properties, it also introduces complexities in alignment and limitations in the independent adjustment and modification of the sample and reference beams.

2.3 Experimental set-up

The experimental setup of the balanced-detection ICAPS gas sensor, incorporating a compact probe laser path via integration of a collimating fiber-array, is illustrated in Figure 4.

Fig. 4 Left: Illustration (section view) of the designed gas cell including the interferometer with a spacing of 1 mm, having a total gas volume of 1.8 cm^3 . Right: Experimental setup. QCL: Quantum Cascade Laser. Diff. Ampl: Differential amplifier. PD1 and PD2: Photodetector 1 and 2. Circ. 1 and circ.2: Circulator 1 and 2. FA: Fiber-array. LIA: Lock-in amplifier.

The setup uses a single air filled FPI device, consisting of two rectangular mirrors, which are deposited on fused silica substrates with the dimension of $10 \text{ mm} \times 5 \text{ mm} \times 2 \text{ mm}$. Both mirrors are coated with a dielectric material, achieving a total reflectivity of 0.989 at the working wavelength of 1550 nm . The cavity mirrors are fixed to each other by two spacers of 1 mm thickness, resulting in an FSR of 1.2 nm . The FWHM was experimentally measured to be $\sim 10 \text{ pm}$, corresponding to a cavity finesse of ~ 120 . Photothermal-induced refractive index changes inside the sample cavity

were monitored via a fiber-coupled single-mode tunable continuous wave distributed feedback fiber laser (CW-DFB-FL), emitting at 1550 nm with an output power of 40 mW. It had a tuning range of 1.2 nm, enabling to scan one *FSR* of the FPI. The probe beam was split in two equal parts through a 50:50 fiber-coupled beam splitter. Each output beam was connected to a fiber-coupled circulator, directing the light to the input connector of the fiber-array. The two probe laser beams were coupled via the microlens array into the interferometric device, forming two cavities. One cavity was used as the transducer for monitoring the induced refractive index changes, while the second cavity was used to apply balanced detection. Light reflected from the FP cavity is redirected through the circulator to a gain-amplified photodetector (PD). Before impinging on the PD, the light passes through a variable optical attenuator (VOA) to prevent saturation of the PD.

The probe laser frequency was maintained at the FPI's inflection point via a slow feedback circuit (mHz), that employs the DC value of the PD at the inflection point as set point. The PD signal is processed to produce the error signal based on deviations from the setpoint. The error signal is then processed through a servo controller to determine the correction signal to adjust the output current of the probe laser driver. By controlling the DC-component, any drift of the transducer, e.g., due to temperature or drift of the emitted laser frequency itself was compensated. The lock to the inflection point of the cavity resonance was ensured for both the sample and reference cavity, as in that position their resonances overlap.

Selective heating of the sample was performed by a collimated, high heat load (HHL) packaged CW-DFB-QCL, emitting at a wavelength of 5.26 μm . The QCL wavelength could be tuned by varying the QCL temperature via injection current and temperature control by a Peltier element.

The collimated excitation beam was focused through the gas cell windows using a plano-convex lens with a 50 mm-focal length. Both, the focusing lens and the windows are made of calcium fluoride (CaF_2) as this material is transparent to the excitation laser wavelength. The distance between the focusing lens and the gas cell was adjusted to ensure that the pump beam waist was aligned with the center of the gas cell. This position facilitates the detection of the photo-induced refractive index change through the intersection of the beam with the probe laser beam within the spacing of the FPI.

The custom-made gas cell schematic is shown in the inset of Figure 4. It features an inlet and an outlet on the top to allow the gas exchange and two CaF_2 windows for the excitation beam transmission. It houses a single interferometric device, which is fixed on one side into the compact and gas-tight aluminum cell, having a total sample volume of $\sim 1.8 \text{ cm}^3$. Transmission of the probe laser beams was enabled directly by the interferometer substrate on the front of the cell and a fused silica window on its back. The FPI was probed using two channels from the fiber-array, positioned 1.25mm apart. One channel detected the photo-induced refractive index change, while the other served as a reference for noise subtraction in the balanced-detection scheme. The fiber-array with its microlenses was enclosed in a customized holder, positioned on a compact 5-axis stage, for fine alignment with the FPI.

The metrological figures of merit for the presented sensor were investigated by employing an excitation modulation frequency of $f_{exc} = 297 \text{ Hz}$, with a modulation depth of $\Delta\nu = \pm 0.25 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, an LIA time constant set to $\tau = 1 \text{ s}$, and a sawtooth excitation laser tuning frequency of $f = 6.67 \text{ mHz}$. The absolute pressure and flow of the sample gas was kept constant at $p = 900 \text{ mbar}$ and $u = 9 \text{ mL min}^{-1}$.

3 EXPERIMENTAL, RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Nitric Oxide Absorption Band Selection

Nitric oxide (NO) was selected as the gas analyte, and exhibits absorption lines which are interference-free from water vapor and other common atmospheric gases. A simulated spectrum of NO R6.5 transitions located at 1900.08 and 1900.52 cm^{-1} , which were selected for measurement is shown in Figure 5. The peak at 1900.08 cm^{-1} in the HITRAN spectrum displayed in Figure 7 has a line strength nearly twice as large as the one at 1900.52 cm^{-1} .

Fig. 5. HITRAN2020 simulated absorption spectrum of 100 ppmv NO ($p = 900$ mbar, $l = 1$ cm, $T = 296$ K).

3.2 FPI probing with a microlensed-coupled fiber-array

The sample and reference probe beam travel very closely within the FA and as they enter and reflect from the cavity. For effective balanced detection it is fundamental that no crosstalk happens within the FA and that the beam emitted from one channel remains isolated and is not detected by an adjacent channel. The occurrence of crosstalk, or the detection of a signal emitted from a different fiber, would lead to reduced performance. Ensuring strict separation and non-interference between channels is therefore essential to maintain the precision and reliability of the system. To investigate crosstalk between the sample and reference channels, an experiment was carried out which tested whether the beam from one fiber is detectable by another.

The experimental setup consisted of one probe laser beam, the FA with its MLA, the FPI and one photodetector. The light emitted from the probe laser was launched into fiber 6 of the FA and then reflected from the FPI. Fiber number 6 is indicated by the red spot on the front view of the schematic MLA in the inset of Figure 6. Light is then detected by the photodiode from fibers 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5, one at a time. For instance, the inset depicts fiber 5, situated at a distance of $250 \mu\text{m}$, with a blue spot. The results, based on varying the probe laser wavelength, demonstrate that signal detection is proportional to fiber proximity.

Fig. 6. Signal detected by fibers 1, 2, 3, 4, 5 when light is launched from fiber 6. Inset: Schematic of front view of the MLA.

Fig. 7. Normalized photodetector response from two channels of the fiber-array, as a function of the probe emission wavelength. The wavelength values were chosen to scan across a resonance of the FPI.

Light output from one channel is reflected by the FPI and partially coupled again to the neighboring channels. The detected intensity of recoupled light declines with increasing lateral displacement. Consequently, for minimizing crosstalk and/or interference, fibers 1 and 6, separated by 1.25 mm, were chosen for balanced detection, showing the smallest crosstalk of this configuration. In balanced-detection ICAPS, utilizing only two channels, the crosstalk between adjacent fibers can be managed. However, when more than two fibers are required, as in the case of multi-spectral and multi-channels detection systems, crosstalk will become a limiting factor for device miniaturization. It is fundamental that the resonances detected by fibers 1 and 6, henceforth called channel 1 and channel 2, are as identical as possible. The recorded resonances, as function of working wavelength, are shown in Figure 7. The resonances show nearly identical responses on the right side of the resonance, but also a mismatch on the left side of the curve. This behavior is most likely caused by the Gaussian nature of the beam, i.e., by its beam divergence [37]–[39]. As the FPI has flat mirrors, after a certain number of roundtrips the beam will eventually start diverging, this divergence will cause the resonances to broad towards shorter wavelengths. Additionally, due to the divergence, a small portion of the reflected light is coupled from the probe channel to the reference channel and vice versa, causing interference of the two channels and yielding a superimposed fringe pattern on the left side. As the long wavelength sides overlap very well, the probe laser was locked at the right-side inflection point. This ensured that the noise was equally transduced from the sample and reference probe beam, therefore improving the sensor's SNR, and hence its sensitivity in terms of minimum detection limit (MDL), and normalized noise equivalent absorption (NNEA).

3.3 Spectral response of the Balanced-Detection ICAPS scheme with fiber-array

To evaluate the balanced-detection ICAPS sensor system's selective response to NO traces, the $2f$ -WM spectra across five different NO concentrations of 20, 40, 60, 80, and 100 ppmv were measured. These concentrations were achieved by diluting 100 ppmv NO with pure nitrogen. All measurements were conducted at an absolute pressure of 900 mbar, a temperature of 296 K and an optimized modulation depth of $\Delta\nu = \pm 0.25 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. Figure 8a illustrates the five recorded $2f$ -WM spectra of NO at varying concentrations, added to the recorded sensor's noise floor for pure N_2 . During the experiments, the QCL frequency was finely tuned over two absorption bands of the R6.5 transition of NO centered at 1900.52 cm^{-1} and 1900.08 cm^{-1} by varying the QCL injection current at a stabilized QCL temperature of $25.5 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. QCL temperature is stabilized through an inner thermoelectric cooler (TEC) and a second for the HHL housing. At this temperature and with a driving current of 473 mA, the QCL emits a pump beam with an optical power of 36.2 mW. The QCL's wavelength is modulated at a frequency $f_{exc} = 297 \text{ Hz}$ through a LIA. The sinusoidal signal at f_{exc} is also used as inner reference signal for the $2f$ -WM demodulation.

Fig.8: a) $2f$ -WM balanced-detection ICAPS spectra of five different NO concentrations together with the noise floor of the sensor for pure N_2 recorded at an absolute pressure of $p = 900 \text{ mbar}$ when the QCL frequency was tuned over the two absorptions bands centered at 1900.52 cm^{-1} and 1900.08 cm^{-1} . b) Linear sensor response of the measured signal amplitudes versus NO gas concentration.

To evaluate the results, the noise was compared to the $2f$ -WM signal, using an integration time of 1 second. Figure 8b displays a graph of the linear sensor response. It plots the measured signal amplitudes at the center of the absorption

band at 1900.08 cm^{-1} against the NO gas concentration levels. The calibration curve includes a linear fit of the data, yielding an R^2 value of 0.9993, confirming the sensor's excellent linearity over the tested concentration.

3.4 Comparative Analysis of Balanced and Non-Balanced Detection

For a more comparative perspective, the differences between balanced and non-balanced detection modes of the ICAPS system using the fiber-array integration are analyzed. The noise of the sensor was recorded when the cell was flushed with pure nitrogen under both the balanced and non-balanced detection scenarios. Noise is measured over a total 60-minute time.

Figure 9 shows the comparison results: balanced detection offers an improvement in noise levels, showing an improvement of the calculated standard deviation by a factor of 7.14. The non-balanced detection mode had a noise standard deviation of 0.0692 mV, while the balanced-detection mode significantly reduced this to a mere 0.0097 mV.

Fig. 9: a) Recorded sensor noise for balanced detection and non-balanced detection mode, showing an improvement in noise by a factor of 7.14 when employing balanced detection. b) Comparison of $2f$ -WM ICAPS spectra of 20 ppmv NO in balanced detection and non-balanced detection mode.

Further information is obtained from the $2f$ -WM ICAPS spectra. The two peaks at 1900.08 and 1900.52 cm^{-1} have the same amplitude both for balanced detection and non-balanced detection. This implies that, during balanced detection, subtracting the reference from the signal only reduces the noise without affecting the signal. Such an observation further confirms that the thermal wave does not propagate to the second channel. If the reference channel were to detect part of the thermal wave, the amplitude of the balanced detection would also decrease.

3.5 Figures of merit calculation

Analysis of the $2f$ -WM ICAPS spectra displayed in Figure 8a combined with the noise data in Figure 9a provides fundamental parameters to determine the minimum detection limit (MDL). This calculation considers the amplitude of the peak at 1s integration time and the standard deviation of the noise. An NO concentration of 20 ppmv yields a peak absorption amplitude of 3.036 mV. In contrast, the standard deviation for pure N_2 is 0.0097 mV. From this data, the derived signal to noise ratio (SNR) is found to be 313, for a final MDL of 64 ppbv with 1s integration time. The normalized noise equivalent absorption (NNEA) ($\text{W cm}^{-1} \text{ Hz}^{-1/2}$) is calculated via

$$NNEA = \frac{P \cdot \alpha_{\min}}{\sqrt{\Delta f_{ENBW}}} = 5.66 \cdot 10^{-8} \text{ W cm}^{-1} \text{ Hz}^{-1/2}, \quad (2)$$

where:

- α_{\min} is the minimum detectable NO absorption coefficient $\alpha_{\min} = 4.79 \times 10^{-7} \text{ cm}^{-1}$,
- P is the optical power of the excitation beam at the absorption peak, $P = 36.2 \text{ mW}$, and
- Δf_{ENBW} is the LIA detector bandwidth, $\Delta f_{ENBW} = 94 \text{ mHz}$.

The *NNEA* is a valuable parameter to assess the performance of gas sensors based on indirect spectroscopy techniques, such as PTS and PAS, as it is independent of gas type, excitation power and detection bandwidth. This enables a direct comparison on diverse indirect gas sensors operating with different detection schemes.

Table 1. Comparison of NNEA for different techniques for photothermal interferometry

Technique	Wavenumber [cm ⁻¹]	Gas analyte	Excitation power [mW]	NNEA [W cm ⁻¹ Hz ^{-1/2}]
ICAPS [31]	1900.7	Nitric oxide (NO)	30	$3.3 \cdot 10^{-6}$
BICAPS [23]	1380.93	Sulphur dioxide (SO ₂)	174	$4.5 \cdot 10^{-9}$
FPI in ARHCF [20]	1900.7	Nitric oxide (NO)	78	$4.29 \cdot 10^{-8}$
Heterodyne MZI [40]	2778	Nitrous oxide (N ₂ O)	1.4	$7.7 \cdot 10^{-9}$
BICAPS <i>this work</i>	1900.8	Nitric oxide (NO)	36.2	$5.66 \cdot 10^{-8}$

CONCLUSION

The presented work demonstrates the implementation of a fiber-array in conjunction with a micro lens array to the balanced-detection ICAPS gas sensing methodology. This new step leads to an improvement in the compactness of the probe laser path of the BICAPS sensor. It allows to couple the sample and reference probe beam with a small lateral spacing of only 1.25 mm into a single FPI device. Balanced detection is a key strategy to achieve highly sensitive and robust gas sensors. The approach of using a fiber-array enables the implementation of balanced detection with highly compact dimensions, overcoming a widely spaced probe and reference beam or the use of two individual interferometers. This advancement in the system's design offers a pathway to developing miniaturized and portable gas sensors.

The fabrication of fiber arrays is a well-established and reliable process, widely employed across various applications. Integrating the fiber-array with the MLA is a critical step because it influences the uniformity and repeatability of the output beams. In BICAPS it is essential that these output beams have highly consistent output characteristics. Additionally, aligning the fiber-array with the FPI needs to be done with high precision to achieve identical resonances.

Future improvements in the assembly process of the FA and MLA are expected to significantly enhance the overall performance and reliability of the BICAPS system by increasing the similarity of the responses of each channel, reducing crosstalk, and enhancing mechanical stability.

This advancement in the system's design offers a pathway to developing miniaturized and portable gas sensors.

Furthermore, small sensing volumes allow for faster gas exchange and therefore faster sensor response. These advantages add to the advantages introduced by the BICAPS technique, as its flexibility regarding excitation wavelength and modulation frequency, its potential to further miniaturization, to higher sensitivity using higher finesse FP cavities, and the fact that it is baseline-free.

The figures of merit of the presented system prove its effectiveness in gas sensing applications. An MDL of 64 ppbv was achieved using a 1 second integration time, corresponding to a NNEA of $5.66 \cdot 10^{-8} \text{ W cm}^{-1} \text{ Hz}^{-1/2}$.

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